

Modernizing NASS's Statistical Disclosure Limitation (SDL) Methodology

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Abstract

The USDA National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) is mandated by Title 7 and the Confidential Information Protection and Statistical Efficiency Act (CIPSEA) to protect the confidentiality of individual information in the production of official statistics. This confidentiality requirement applies to data released to the public and to other agencies. Currently, for the Census of Agriculture, NASS uses cell suppression methodology, developed in the 1990s, to protect sensitive tabular data from public disclosure. The goal of cell suppression is to reduce the risk of disclosure by first identifying sensitive cells for primary suppression and then finding additional cells for complementary suppression to protect the primary cells from attackers. Complementary suppressions are chosen using network flow methodology. From October 2021 to March 2022, NASS reviewed disclosure methodologies and identified six methods for further study. This presentation discusses the Statistical Disclosure Limitation (SDL) research being conducted to improve NASS's SDL methodology and shares the roadmap for modernizing NASS's SDL procedures.

Key Words: Statistical Disclosure Limitation, Cell suppression, Linear programming, Network flow

1. Motivation of SDL Modernization

1.1 Background

The USDA's National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) is legally required to protect the confidentiality of individual information in the production of official statistics, as mandated by Title 18, U.S. Code, Sections 1905 and 1902, Title 7, U.S. Code, Section 2276, and the Confidential Information Protection and Statistical Efficiency Act (CIPSEA) of 2018, Title III of the Evidence Act. This confidentiality requirement applies to data released to the public and other agencies. The current NASS cell suppression methodology, based on a linear program called "Minimum Cost Flow," was developed in the late 1990s (Cox 1995). Since then, new disclosure protection methodologies have emerged. The NASS Statistical Disclosure Limitation (SDL) team is researching and evaluating these new methodologies to recommend a foundation for NASS's disclosure system, which is set to be implemented by 2026.

This section describes the cell suppression methodology currently used at NASS, introduced by Jewett (1993) in the 1990s and based on a Minimum Cost Flow (MCF) algorithm. Section 2 presents the process of identifying six methods for evaluation: cell suppression with general linear programming, Controlled Tabular Adjustment (CTA), Random Tabular Adjustment (RTA), Noise method, Synthetic Data Approach, and Differential Privacy methods. From this effort, two new SDL approaches were identified. Section 3 introduces an innovative cell suppression method based on a new data utility cost function and a new optimal solver. Section 4 discusses the RTA-PRDP method,

which combines the RTA sensitivity rule with Per-Record Differential Privacy (PRDP) noise addition. Finally, future efforts for the SDL modernization project are outlined.

1.2 Cell suppression method

For cell suppression, sensitive cells are referred to as primary suppressions. These are table cells that could reveal individual respondent information and are identified after tabulation. At NASS, identifying sensitive cells involves two parts: 1) the p -percent rule, from the Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology (FCSM) Statistical Working Paper #22, for magnitude data; and 2) threshold rules for frequency data. These primary suppressions are defined first and withheld from publication.

One of the most common methods to protect sensitive cells is suppression. In a row or column with a suppressed sensitive cell, at least one additional cell must be suppressed. Otherwise, the value in the sensitive cell could be calculated by subtraction from the marginal total. Therefore, some non-sensitive cells must also be suppressed to protect primary suppressions. These are referred to as complementary suppressions.

Using a linear sensitivity measure, disclosure limitation methods are applied to cells where a respondent's data may be estimated too closely. For the p -percent rule, the linear sensitivity measure is based on whether an attacker can estimate a respondent's reported value within $p\%$. A tabulation cell is declared sensitive if the upper or lower estimates for a respondent's value are closer to the reported value than a pre-specified percentage p . This method assumes that before data are published, a user can estimate the true value to within plus or minus 100%.

For frequency data, each respondent contributes the same amount. Therefore, all linear sensitivity measures default to a threshold rule, and a cell is considered sensitive if there are too few respondents.

Linear programming is the most common procedure for detecting suppression patterns in tables because it can be used for higher-dimensional tables. Network procedures have been shown to provide fast solutions for two-dimensional tables. The network flow method for cell suppression is self-auditing only for two-dimensional tables with a hierarchy in one dimension. However, it is not self-auditing for two-dimensional tables with hierarchical structures in both rows and columns, nor for three- or higher-dimensional tables with hierarchical structures.

Software that automatically selects complementary cells for suppression has been available since the 1970s at the U.S. Census Bureau and Statistics Canada. These programs typically use linear programming methods, implemented by accessing general-purpose linear programming routines that leverage special structures in the data. Due to refinements in linear programming algorithms, these routines now run much faster than in the 1980s. Network flow methods can be viewed as a special case of linear programming. They work best for two-dimensional tables with at most one level of hierarchy in either rows or columns. Routines based on network flow methods are typically much faster than linear programming routines. Cell suppression programs can be used for both magnitude data tables and frequency data tables. In the past 20 years, considerable research has focused on developing faster and more efficient procedures for both two-dimensional and three-dimensional tables. This research has involved methods based on integer programming, network flow theory, and neural networks.

2. Timeline of SDL Modernization Project

2.1 Phase 1 studies: Review of literature and practice

The NASS SDL Modernization project began in October 2021. From October 2021 to March 2022, the Research and Development Division (RDD) and the Methodology Division (MD) conducted Phase 1 SDL studies. As part of this effort, six seminars were organized:

Table 1: RDD SDL seminar series

Date	Invited speaker	Affiliation
September 30, 2021	Natalie Shlomo	University of Manchester
October 13, 2021	Jerome Reiter	Duke University
October 26, 2021	Mark Stinner	Statistics Canada
November 16, 2021	Philip Steel	US Census Bureau
December 2, 2021	John M. Abowd	US Census Bureau
March 29, 2022	Natalie Shlomo	University of Manchester

Invited speakers provided references for disclosure-related papers and books prior to their seminars. The study group reviewed these materials, conducted 16 weekly group presentations and discussions, and focused on applications for agricultural data, such as the Census of Agriculture (COA). They also listed the pros and cons of the SDL methods studied.

With this background, the study group selected 6 methods for further study.

- Cell suppression method with General Linear Programming (Kelly et. al., 1992, Cox, 1995).
- Controlled Tabular Adjustment (Cox and Dandekar, 2002; Dulá *et al.*, 2004).
- Random Tabular adjustment (Stinner, 2017).
- Noise method (Evans *et al.*, 1996; Massell and Funk, 2007).
- Synthetic Data Approach (Reiter, 2005; Kinney *et al.*, 2011).
- Differential Privacy (Rinott *et al.*, 2018; Dwork and Roth, 2014; Abowd and Schmutte, 2015).

2.2 SDL phase 2 studies

For Phase 2 of the SDL studies, an agency-wide NASS SDL research team was formed. The team's purpose was to organize and conduct systematic research on disclosure methods based on the SDL Phase 1 studies. The initial focus was on methods such as the suppression method with general linear programming, Controlled Tabular Adjustment (CTA), Random Tabular Adjustment (RTA), the synthetic data approach, and the Differential Privacy method. Other methods could be considered as determined by the team. Ultimately, the SDL research team aims to identify and evaluate an innovative statistical disclosure method for the 2027 Census of Agriculture (COA).

For the evaluation, comparative analyses have been conducted between new methods under consideration and the current NASS disclosure methodology (suppression method with minimum cost flow) using the 2017 Census of Agriculture (COA) data. The methods prototyped using the 2017 data will then be applied to the 2022 data, followed by a comparative analysis between the new methods and the current NASS disclosure methodology. Based on these analyses, the team will make recommendations on an SDL approach to the NASS Business Council and senior leadership team for implementation on an agreed-upon set of surveys by 2025. The new SDL methodology and system are to be fully operational in 2026 for the 2027 COA.

From November 2022 to April 2025, the NASS SDL research team is exploring and identifying a statistical disclosure method for the 2027 Census of Agriculture (COA). The three expected results are:

- Recommend a disclosure methodology that meets government-wide and departmental requirements for the 2027 Census of Agriculture.
- Draft a computing solution, either through existing software or by developing new programs, for the proposed disclosure methodology.
- Develop evaluation metrics to ensure compliance with the law and Statistical Policy Working Paper 22 (v2, 2005) - Report on Statistical Disclosure Limitation Methodology.

In addition, the SDL team aims to build disclosure knowledge, promote new disclosure methodologies, and share SDL research activities within NASS and the broader statistical community.

On March 31, 2023, the NASS SDL team established three sub-teams, one for each of three research directions:

- Cell suppression methods, which extend the current disclosure method used in production work, especially those using general Linear Programming.
- Model-based methods for tabular data (magnitude and frequency tables), such as Controlled Tabular Adjustment (CTA), Random Tabular Adjustment (RTA), and the Noise method.
- Methods that model the microdata, including the Synthetic data and Differential Privacy methods

NASS established a small contract with Tumult Labs to explore the feasibility of using differential privacy, a gold standard for disclosure avoidance, on the Census of Agriculture. Tumult scientists collaborated with NASS subject-matter experts to gain a thorough understanding of the identified data product and then delivered a feasibility report evaluating the applicability of differential privacy.

On March 31, 2024, SDL team began to focus on two SDL approaches and reorganized into two sub-teams:

- New Cell Suppression Approach: Focused on proposing a new data utility cost function and programming a new optimal solver.
- RTA-PRDP Method: Aimed at combining the RTA sensitivity rule with Per-Record Differential Privacy (PRDP) noise addition.

3. New Cell Suppression Approach

3.1 Current NASS disclosure method

NASS uses the p -percent rule to identify sensitive data cells at risk of disclosure for the Census of Agriculture, the Puerto Rico Census of Agriculture, and follow-on programs such as the Farm and Ranch Irrigation Survey and the Census of Aquaculture. The threshold rule is also applied to all magnitude data to ensure that a minimum of three farms is represented in each published cell; cells with fewer than three farms are also suppressed. The value of p is administratively determined and consistent across all publications. Complementary suppressions are chosen using network flow methodology. Frequency count data are not considered sensitive and are not subject to suppression. NASS statisticians are responsible for identifying primary suppressions and their complements and ensuring that the suppression patterns are consistent over time.

Every five years, NASS conducts the Census of Agriculture. NASS uses the p -percent rule to identify sensitive cells in tables but does not publish the value of p . Sensitive cells are suppressed, and complementary suppressions are identified using the network flow technique. Network flow is ideal for two-dimensional tables and has also been applied to three-dimensional tables. However, for three-dimensional tables, linear programming is the preferred method from a theoretical standpoint, as it guarantees full protection of sensitive cells and eliminates the need for a disclosure audit program to check the extent of protection achieved.

Let T be the weighted total of a cell to be released, U_1 be the unweighted value of the largest operation in the cell, and U_2 be the unweighted value of the second largest operation in the cell. Then, by the p -percent rule, the cell is sensitive when the following inequality holds:

$$T - U_1 - U_2 \leq U_1 \times (p/100).$$

Sensitive cells are suppressed as primary suppressions. The minimum amount of required protection (Req) by the $p\%$ rule is defined as $U_1 \times (p/100) - R$, where R is the total value of remaining cell

contributors, i.e., $R = T - U_1 - U_2$. The protection interval is equal to [true cell value - Req, true cell value + Req]. Req is also used when to identify cells for complementary suppressions. Complementary cell suppressions are expected to guarantee that exact interval estimates (lower and upper bounds) of the value of each suppressed sensitive cell are at a safe distance from the actual cell value within an interval at least as broad as that defined by minimum amount of required protection (Cox 2002).

To protect primary suppressions, complementary suppressions are needed. To identify those cells, the table is first converted to a network flow diagram. Secondly, the network is used to identify cells as complementary suppressions for the sensitive cells. The groups must form a closed circuit and contain the sensitive cells. To find the best path in the network flow, network methodology is applied to minimize the data utility cost of selecting complementary suppressions. The cost function associated with the loss of information due to cell suppression is defined as

$$\text{cost} = \sum_i c_i x_i,$$

where c_i is cost/information loss and x_i is the flow variable for each cell i .

At NASS, Jewett (1993) introduced the minimal cost flow program, which was initially coded using a Fortran66 compliant solver. This program was later converted to SAS. SAS includes an optimal solver, τ -Argus, which is used by Statistics Canada for many agricultural surveys, by the USDA Farm Production and Conservation (FPAC) in its disclosure system and is widely used in the European Union (EU). τ -Argus can provide the exact optimal algorithm and a near-optimal solution to the Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) formulation. As an alternative, the Energy Information Agency's (EIA's) disclosure program uses the software package CPLEX to perform Linear Programming (LP).

Here's a summary of the NASS cell suppression programs:

- Identify sensitive cells as primary suppressions.
- Find additional cells as the complementary suppressions to protect the primary cells against an attacker.
- Transfer the cell suppression problem to a linear programming problem.
- Build network flow models for two-dimensional tables.
- Minimize cost: $\sum_i c_i x_i$, where c_i is cost and x_i is the flow variable for each cell i .

3.2 New cell suppression Approach

Since data utility is considered as total value or total number, we propose a new data utility cost function that includes both total value and total number; that is,

$$\alpha \sum_i x_i + \sum_i a_i x_i \tag{1}$$

where $x_i = 0$ or 1 , a_i is the total value of cell i , and α is a tuning parameter for balancing the two data utility measures. When $\alpha = 0$, the cost function is based only on the magnitude, and many small-value cells are suppressed. As α increases, a few cells with large values, such as some totals, will be suppressed and more cells with small values will be published (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Total Number/Value of Complementary Cells vs α

For software, CPLEX was adopted as a replacement for the Fortran66 compliant solver. CPLEX was applied to groups of primary cells instead of sequentially to a queue of all the primary suppressions. Programs to solve the MIP problem were developed in R and CPLEX for simulated datasets.

Another improvement is referred to as problem reduction (Skip-P). If one primary cell can be protected by other primary cells, it is not necessary to identify cells for complementary suppression (Skip-P). If a primary cell can be “skipped,” its constraints can be removed from the mixed-integer programming problem. This reduces the problem scale (number of constraints) and improves computational efficiency. The complexity of the mixed-integer programming problem is exponential in the number of primary suppressions, so a small reduction in the number of primary cells can substantially reduce running time.

The evaluation method for cell suppression proposed by De Wolf (2002) was assessed in τ -ARGUS using simulated datasets. Based on exploratory analyses, the new MIP model was found to significantly improve data utility and reduce disclosure risk when using the proposed cost function in equation (1) and the commercial solver CPLEX, compared to existing methods. For hierarchical structure tables, the team proposes using the top-down methods proposed by De Wolf (2002), which avoid backtracking and reduce computational time.

In addition to statistical measures, such as relative absolute difference of utility and risk for data altered through cell suppression, an attack indicator ($I(e)$) was developed as a key evaluation criterion for a point estimate e for a primary cell with value x :

$$\text{attack indicator: } I(e) = \max \left(0, 1 - \frac{|e - x|}{Req} \right)$$

Properties of the attack indicator are following:

1. $I(e) \in [0,1]$.
2. If $I(e) = 0$, then the attack failed since e is totally outside the protection interval.
3. If $I(e) = 1$, then $e = x$ exactly.
4. If $I(e) \in (0,1)$, then x is partially successfully attacked. The higher $I(e)$, the closer e is to x .

Based on the attack indicator, under-suppression cells can be identified as follows:

1. When $0 < \text{attack indicator} < 1$, the cell is partially attacked.
2. When $\text{attack indicator} = 1$, the cell is fully attacked, which means that the attacker’s estimation equals the true cell value.

For some tables, under-suppressions are inevitable, especially for small and sparse tables because too many cells are published.

4. RTA-PRDP Method

4.1 Random Tabular Adjustment (RTA)

Statistics Canada introduced a disclosure-control model based largely on Bayesian decision theory called Random Tabular Adjustment (RTA). This method controls the risk of disclosure by randomly adjusting the data and is intended as an alternative to the common practice of suppressing cells at many statistical agencies. Statistics Canada has applied RTA for its census and numerous agricultural surveys. This method involves a trade-off between the utility of the published data and the risk of disclosing confidential data. Disclosure control methods aim to assess and control the risk of disclosing confidential data while providing researchers with useful statistical data.

For Randomized Tabular Adjustment (RTA), the values of sensitive cells are randomly altered to ensure that an attacker cannot estimate individual contributions with a precision better than a prescribed threshold (Stinner, 2017). Sensitive cells are identified using the rule of prior-posterior sensitivity, a probabilistic approach where random noise is added to each sensitive cell. There are two types of users or attackers:

1. Analytical user: A person interested in data summaries, but not in confidential (record-level) information.
2. Confidential user: A person interested in confidential, record-level information (real attacker).

The National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) aims to protect the table by maximizing utility for analytical users while minimizing the risk of exposing confidential data.

Under Randomized Tabular Adjustment (RTA), the distributions (knowledge) of data users/attackers and a baseline distribution are assumed to be known. The two knowledge distributions (base and prior) are assumed to be normal distributions, while the baseline distribution is user specific. Utility, risk, and disclosure control parameters are defined within this model. The RTA model aims to find the disclosure control parameter values that maximize utility and limit disclosure risk. Cells that requiring random noise are identified based on the value of the disclosure control parameter. Random noise, generated through posterior analyses, is added to the original value of the sensitive cell. The posterior distribution is a function of the disclosure control parameter (σ^2). Once the value of σ^2 that maximizes utility and bounds disclosure risk is determined, random noise is generated from a normal distribution with a mean of zero and variance σ^2 . This noise is then added to the original cell total. If the calculated σ^2 value is not positive, the original cell value remains unaltered. Generally, not all cells in a table are affected by RTA; only sensitive cells and totals are impacted.

4.2 Differential Privacy

Differential Privacy (Rinott et al., 2018; Dwork and Roth, 2014; Abowd and Schmutte, 2015) is a mathematically rigorous framework for releasing statistical information about datasets while protecting the privacy of individual data subjects. It allows a data holder to share aggregate patterns of the group while limiting the information that can be inferred about specific individuals. This is achieved by injecting carefully calibrated noise into statistical computations, preserving the utility of the statistics while provably limiting what can be inferred about any individual in the dataset. Differential Privacy provides a mathematically provable privacy guarantee against all types of attacks.

Privacy mechanism: A randomized algorithm $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ with domain $\mathbb{N}^{|\mathcal{X}|}$ is ϵ -differentially private if for all $S \subseteq \text{Range}(\mathcal{M})$, and for all $x, y \in \mathbb{N}^{|\mathcal{X}|}$ such that $\|x - y\|_1 \leq 1$,

$$\Pr(\mathcal{M}(x) \in S) \leq \exp(\epsilon) \Pr(\mathcal{M}(y) \in S)$$

where ϵ -differential privacy ensures that, for every run of the mechanism $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$, the output observed is (almost) equally likely to be observed on every neighboring database simultaneously.

Differential Privacy is considered the gold standard for disclosure avoidance. Unlike legacy methods such as cell suppression, it injects noise into the data. The algorithm and its parameters are fully transparent. Differential Privacy is widely deployed and gaining widespread acceptance. Privacy loss is bounded by the privacy loss budget (ϵ), which serves as a knob to adjust the tradeoff between data privacy and accuracy. A smaller ϵ means more noise is added. When ϵ approaches infinity, the public-use data file is the same as the original data. Conversely, when ϵ approaches zero, the public-use data file becomes useless due to excessive noise. The U.S. Census Bureau applied the Differential Privacy method to the 2020 Census.

Differential Privacy with formal privacy guarantees may provide solutions at NASS because most agricultural statistics involve summation. Sensitivity Δf of the sum (e.g., acreage) is the maximum possible change in the sum when a single record's data is added/removed. The noised cell $M(D)$ is

$$M(D) = \text{Sum}(D) + \text{Lap}\left(\frac{\Delta f}{\epsilon}\right)$$

where $\text{Sum}(D)$ is true value of cell and $\text{Lap}\left(\frac{\Delta f}{\epsilon}\right)$ is a Laplace distribution with mean zero and variance of $2\left(\frac{\Delta f}{\epsilon}\right)^2$.

Tumult Analytics and OpenDP are two of the most popular Differential Privacy software. OpenDP is a community effort, not owned or directed by a single corporation. It provides a system of tools for enabling privacy-protective analysis of sensitive personal data. Tumult Analytics, owned by Tumult Labs, is built on a sophisticated privacy foundation that mediates access to sensitive data; every program and application comes with an embedded proof of privacy. Both software packages are written in Python.

4.3 Per-Record Differential Privacy

As with many establishment surveys or censuses, agricultural data present key privacy challenges, such as high skewness (some cells dominated by a few farms) and small sums (leading to a high suppression rate for county and other small areas, resulting in over-suppression). These issues are exacerbated by weighted data. Differential Privacy often has poor privacy/utility tradeoffs on highly skewed data. When a table is dominated by a few records with large, reported values, sensitivity becomes high, resulting in excessive noise being added to the cells. To address this, NASS and Tumult Labs have proposed a relaxed version of Differential Privacy, called per-record differential privacy (PRDP), which offers DP-style guarantees in skewed-data settings.

Per-Record Differential Privacy (PRDP) (Seeman et al., 2023) is a generalization of standard Differential Privacy, developed to offer nuanced privacy guarantees for highly skewed data. PRDP is an emerging formal privacy notion with the following advantages:

- Provides quantifiable privacy protection against strong adversarial models.
- Does not require suppression, allowing for increased transparency.
- Offers sliding protection that enables better utility on skewed data.
- Captures the privacy impact of weighted data.

There are three turning parameters for the PRDP method: 1) privacy loss parameter ϵ ; 2) privacy threshold T – divide a large unit into many small units with value T or less; and 3) (optional) suppression threshold $k\sigma$ - suppress overly noisy data. The noise variance is in proportion to T/ϵ . PRDP offers a Differential Privacy-style guarantee. The level of privacy protection depends on the privacy threshold parameter (T). Cell contributors with values less than T receive full Differential Privacy protection. Those with values greater than T receive partial protection. In addition, we can optionally suppress high-noise cells with suppression threshold $k\sigma$.

Figure 2: PRDP Impact on Suppressing Cells

For the current cell suppression approach, 64% of the county-level estimates are suppressed. As ϵ increases under PRDP, the number of cells suppressed decreases (see Figure 2). When the suppression threshold is 2σ and the privacy is set to $\epsilon = 1$, the percentage of suppressed cells is reduced by 13%; setting the privacy to $\epsilon = 2$ reduces the percentage of suppressed cells by 25%.

PRDP algorithm:

1. Cell i in the table with cell value $x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$; and x_{ij} is the value of unit j in the cell $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i$; and $x_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} x_{ij}$.
2. Skewness exists at the unit level; specifically, a few units have extra-large values, and most units are small.
3. Privacy threshold:
 - Let $x_{(i,j)}$ be order statistics in the cell i , that is, $x_{(i,1)}, x_{(i,2)}, \dots, x_{(i,n_i)}$.
 - Let q be a percentage of the total units of cell i .
 - For example, $q=50$, privacy threshold (T_i) is median of $\{x_i\}$; that is,

$$T_i = \text{median}\{x_i\} = \begin{cases} \left(x_{(\frac{i}{2})} + x_{(\frac{i}{2})+1}\right) & \text{when } n_i \text{ is even} \\ x_{(\frac{i+1}{2})} & \text{when } n_i \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$
4. Noise injection is based on both T_i and ϵ , where ϵ is privacy loss budget:
 - Laplace noise: $\delta_i \sim \text{Lap}\left(0, \frac{T_i}{\epsilon}\right)$.
 - Add noise: $x_i^* = x_i + \delta_i$.
5. A new table with cell $x_i^*, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

4.4 RTA-PRDP method

NASS is exploring a novel methodology to modernize the disclosure limitation techniques applied to the release of their numerous data products from agricultural censuses and surveys. NASS is also mandated to use disclosure avoidance on the released data products to ensure the privacy of the respondents.

The proposed RTA-PRDP method combines Per-Record Differential Privacy (PRDP) with legacy cell suppression methods for disclosure avoidance. This method is a compromise between suppression and noise addition techniques. The RTA-PRDP method consists of three components:

1. Identify sensitive cells using the prior-posterior sensitivity rule.
2. Add noise to the sensitive cells using the PRDP method.

3. Suppress cells with excessively high noise variance based on utility measurements.

Given a dataset and an associated table to be protected, assume that some of the cells in the table are known to be non-sensitive (i.e., do not need protection). Classify the cells of the table into two categories based on sensitivity: sensitive cells and non-sensitive cells. Apply the PRDP method to the sensitive cells. Update the table by substituting only the sensitive cells with their altered values, leaving the values of the non-sensitive cells unchanged. Finally, publish the table.

5. Next Step for SDL Project

The NASS SDL team plans to conduct Phase 3 studies from May 2025 to April 2026. The tasks include:

- Choosing one disclosure avoidance method for the 2027 Census of Agriculture (COA).
- Building a NASS disclosure control system in the Phase 3 studies, which includes statistical analysis, disclosure avoidance methods, evaluation metrics, and flexible output.
- Continuing SDL research to improve the NASS disclosure control system.
- Communicating new disclosure methods and practices within NASS.
- Modernizing NASS disclosure review procedures and practices.

References

Abowd, J., and Schmutte, I., 2015, “Economic analysis and statistical disclosure limitation”, Brookings Papers on Economic Activity, Spring.

Cox, L.H., 1995, “Network models for complementary cell suppression”, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 90, 1453–1462.

Cox, L. and R. Dandekar, 2002, “A disclosure limitation method for tabular data that preserves data accuracy and ease-of-use”, unpublished manuscript.

De Wolf, P.P. (2002), HiTaS: A Heuristic Approach to Cell Suppression in Hierarchical Tables’, In: ‘Inference Control in Statistical Databases. Domingo-Ferrer (Ed.), Springer (Lecture notes in computer science; Vol. 2316)

Dulá, J., Fagan, J., and Massell, P., 2004, “Tabular Statistical Disclosure Control: Optimization Techniques in Suppression and Controlled Tabular Adjustment”, U.S. Bureau of the Census Research Report Series: 2004-04.

Dwork, C. and Roth, A., 2014, “The Algorithmic Foundations of Differential Privacy”, *Foundations and Trends in Theoretical Computer Science*”.

Evans, T., Zayatz, L., and Slanta, J., 1998, “Using Noise for Disclosure Limitation of Establishment Tabular Data”, *Journal of Official Statistics*.

Federal Committee on Statistical Methodology, 2005, “STATISTICAL POLICY WORKING PAPER 22 - Report on Statistical Disclosure Limitation Methodology”.

Jewett, R. 1993, "Disclosure Analysis for the 1992 Economic Census," unpublished manuscript, Economic Programming Division, Bureau of Census, Washington, DC. <http://www.census.gov/srd/sdc/Jewett.disc.econ.1992.pdf>.

Kelly, J.P., Golden, B.L, Assad, A.A., 1992, “Cell Suppression: disclosure protection for sensitive tabular data”, *Networks* 22, 28–55.

Kinney, S., Reiter, J., Reznick, A., Miranda, J., Jarmin, R., and Abowd, J., 2011, "Towards unrestricted public use business microdata: The synthetic Longitudinal Business Database", *Int. Stat. Rev.*

Massell, P. and Funk, J., 2007, "Protecting the Confidentiality of Tables by Adding Noise to the Underlying Microdata", *ICES-III Proceedings*.

Reiter, J. 2005, "Releasing multiply imputed, synthetic public use microdata: an illustration and empirical study", *J. R. Statist. Soc. A*.

Rinott, Y., O'Keefe, C., Shlomo, N., and Skinner, C., 2018, "Confidentiality and Differential Privacy in the Dissemination of Frequency Tables", *Statistical Science*.

Seeman, J., Sexton, W., Pujol, D., Machanavajjhala, A., 2023, "Privately Answering Queries on Skewed Data via Per Record Differential Privacy". In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.12827*.

Stinner, M., 2017, "Disclosure Control and Random Tabular Adjustment", *SSC Annual Meeting 2017 Proceedings of the Survey Methods Section*.